

LARGE DATA SETS & RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS: A FEASIBLE APPROACH TO LEARNING MUSIC?

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ABSTRACT

One of the critical challenges in music teaching is providing ways for students to search easily across very large amounts of music data, in order that they can build intuition and gain experience around the ways in which different music styles are comprised. This paper demonstrates how MusicXML can be used to create large music data sets that can be utilized for searching and recommendation, in order to facilitate music learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper will outline a methodology to facilitate exploration across large bodies of musical information. The methodology will utilize the data-format MusicXML, showing that it can be used to create data sets that are both amenable to searching, and for deriving recommendations. The motivation behind this methodology is to enhance the understanding that music learners can gain in regard to the mechanics that underlie different music styles, and to facilitate the exploration of music for those who have limited experience with complex music scores.

Having access to extremely large corpuses of music, rendered as data, is a growing phenomenon, especially in recent years. The field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR), here characterized as ‘having access to increased bodies of music and the accompanying challenges of how to extract meaningful music content information’ [1] is growing rapidly. Solutions that, up until recently, have been regarded as impossible (such as the automated transcription of complex music [2,3,4] and the automated optical recognition of music scores for the purpose of converting this into MIDI and MusicXML data [5] are becoming a reality. Music is also far more available than it has been in the past: there is a vast and growing amount of music scores and music recordings to be found online (seen in such initiatives as the IMSLP and Petrucci Music Library [6]. Additionally, the belief that the transcription of recorded music can only be accurately achieved through manual means is increasingly being challenged by a growing number of technological solutions that can accomplish this task [7]. The changing nature by which music data is obtained is part of the wider technological

phenomenon of ‘Big Data’, characterised by vast data sets becoming available and being amenable to nuanced interrogation [8]. However, with the increased access to music in the form of data comes the increased challenge in finding ways to understand and iterate through this data.

This paper will show how MusicXML can be prepared as a mineable data set, provide examples of how data search functionality can be implemented across this data, and demonstrate a way in which prediction and recommendation can be implemented. It will suggest further applications and research that are applicable to both music teaching and music prediction. The code for this paper has been written in Python and can be downloaded and perused at the code repository service, GitHub¹.

2. DATA PREPARATION

MusicXML is a well-formed subset of the XML data format and was purpose designed to capture, as a data set, the various attributes that can be seen on a music score (in terms of western musical notation). Currently the data attributes number around 650, and include such things as: clef, time signature, tempo, lyrics, written annotations, part names etc. Since its introduction in 2004, MusicXML has become ‘the most quickly adopted symbolic music interchange format since MIDI’ [9]. MusicXML is now well established in the Music Information Retrieval field as a promising vehicle by which to drive the design and inform the data-stores of music related applications [5].

To prepare the MusicXML data-set under consideration, the data was first parsed using the python Music21 module, an API developed at MIT specifically for music analysis [10]. This allowed the MusicXML data to be transformed into a nested Python dictionary structure. The initial testing set of MusicXML data (forming the corpus) consisted of the music scores of two pieces of music: a movement from a Beethoven String quartet and a transcription of Keith Jarrett jazz piano solo². Each of these pieces of music was divided into logically named parts, where each part can be regarded as what occurs on a single music stave on the score. For the Beethoven ex-

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¹ <https://github.com/jgab3103/music-app>

² Beethoven’s String Quartet No. 2, Op. 59, 4th Movement, and a transcription of Keith Jarrett solo on Autumn Leaves, taken from the [Tokyo 1996](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1996) live album.

ample, the parts were named, vln_1, vln_2, vla, and vlc, signifying the instrumental parts within a string quartet.

Creating the parts in the jazz example was more complex, and the MusicXML data was prepared using not only the transcription but also the jazz lead sheet of the song under consideration, which listed the song's harmonic progression. Each voice in the harmonic progression was given its own part, consisting of root, third, fifth, seventh, ninth, eleventh and thirteenth. The transcribed solo was given its own part also. A visualization of this data, prior to being rendered into MusicXML, can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Each part was then broken up into a series of events (either note events or rest events) and these events can best be intuited as any occurring note or rest in a musical passage on a given music staff. Information regarding the note or rest event's duration, the midi-frequency (listed as -1 if it was a rest event) and the note or rest event's position was captured. The position of the note was regarded as being relative to the bar of music so, for example, if the time signature of the part was currently 4/4, and the note or rest event occurred on the 3rd beat of the bar, the value would be captured as .75 (being three quarters of the way through a 4/4 bar). The resulting data structure parts and note and rest events can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2

To facilitate the searching of this data set, each note or rest event was given a unique name that could act as an index. This name was created from a concatenation of various elements that were extracted from the parsed data. These elements were: 1) the bar in which the note or rest event occurred; 2) the relative position in the bar the note or rest event occurred and 3) the current tempo (in beats per minute). An example of such a concatenated string is "123_.75_120", here indicating the 123rd bar in a particular part, located at a position three quarters between the start and end of the bar, and having a current tempo of 120 beats per minute.

Although the sample data set is here quite limited, it is important to note that that this data set could be arbitrarily large. It could be all Beethoven's string quartets, or all string quartets, or all of Keith Jarrett's jazz solos. Regardless of what style pieces of music are perceived to be, they here form part of the same corpus.

During the data preparation stage a number of utility functions were also created. The most notable of these were, firstly, a graphing function (using Python's Matplotlib library) that allowed the visualization of a series of note or rest events within a part, similar to the piano roll view editor often found in digital audio workstation (DAW) software. Secondly, a write-to-MIDI function was created using the Python library MIDIutil that allowed the data set to be written to an output midi file, which can be heard, or easily converted back into MusicXML format in software packages such as Sibelius and MuseScore.

Considering the vast array of attributes that can be found in MusicXML as well as the sonic qualities of audio music generally, it is worth noting that there is a great deal

that has been left out during the creation of the data set. Information regarding things such as timbre, score annotation and dynamics are absent. The data set has been purpose designed as a searchable index of frequencies, the relative time at which frequencies occur, and the speed (i.e. tempo) at which they occur. Collecting just this information is enough to inform a highly useful search engine.

3. DATA SEARCH TO FACILITATE LEARNING

With the data structured in the manner above, where each note or rest event was indexed, it became possible to search in order to seek specific and similar musical situations. It became possible to look for the occurrences of specific chords or harmonic progressions across a large corpus of music. It also became possible to see how things such as different tempo could influence note choice, or to examine similar passages in different key signatures. The design of the data set allowed multi-parameter searching across parameters such as piece name, part name, tempo, duration, time-signature, position in bar and time signature.

As an example of the kind of learning that could be facilitated with this data set, consider a student of jazz who wishes to search for all instances of minor 7 flat 5 chord that occurs in all jazz examples within a given corpus, regardless of key. The motivating question of the student is to gain an understanding of how different musicians improvise on this chord. To undertake such a search, it is possible to iterate through the parts, firstly finding any part named 'root'. If this part is found, it is possible to compare the distance between midi frequencies of the root part to other parts of the same piece of music (here the third, fifth and seventh part) that occur at the same time (i.e. same bar and position in bar). If the distances indicated are 3, 6 and 10 (respectively indicating a minor third, flattened fifth, and flattened seventh), a suitable candidate has been found, and can be returned to the user.

As an alternate learning example, consider a student of orchestration wishes to look across a large corpus, which could include all the orchestral works of Prokofiev, Mahler, Stravinsky, and Ravel. The student might wish to seek all the examples where there is a solo cello part that occurs in the cello's upper range (i.e. above G4), where the tempo is between 60bpm and 80bpm. This would return all examples of passages of solo cello in a slow tempo setting, and would allow the student to gain an intuition into the different ways composers write for solo cello at this tempo and range. Rather than relying on standard rules of thumb about how to orchestrate in this setting (i.e. that the violas will often take on the traditional role of cellos when the cello is playing in a higher range at a slow tempo) this provides the student with concrete examples and intuitions about those times composers choose to move away from things that are typically done.

These types of searches, while useful, are fairly simplistic. A student may not wish to have to rely on part names from which to derive information. What if a student, rather than seeking all minor 7 flat 5 chords in jazz pieces within the corpus, was seeking all instances of minor 7 flat 5 chords that occur, regardless of how they are voiced. (i.e. in root position or inversion). Because a minor 7th flat 5 chord can be characterised by the set of distances between the midi-frequencies of various parts, it is possible to calculate this, and search for it. For example, a C minor 7 flat 5 chord, consisting of the notes C, E flat, G flat and B flat can be characterised by the list of distances that occur between each note, in this case [3, 3, 4, 2] seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Note that in order to be able to locate a C minor 7 flat 5 chord from any voicing or inversion that may appear across various parts, the various frequencies under consideration need to first be collected and arranged in the manner of Figure 4, building chord structures by successively taking the note that is the shortest distance away. For example, if the note C is found in one part, and the notes B flat, E Flat and G flat are found in other parts at the same time, the chord can then be constructed by taking the note the shortest distance away from C (the B flat), and then by taking the note the shortest distance from the B flat (the G flat) and finally appending the E flat. This creates an ordered list of distances (being [3, 3, 4, 2]) that can be used to define a minor 7 flat 5 chord. If the chord appears in first inversion, the ordered list will hold, simply starting at a different point and wrapping around (becoming the list of distances of [3,4,2,3]).

Figure 4

This kind of search makes it possible to interrogate the corpus in order to seek occurrences of a particular chord

type, regardless of its voicing or the parts in which it occurs. One of the benefits of this type of searching is that it allows students to explore similar sonorities regardless of the style in which they are occurring, and hear different chord structures in different contexts. If, for example, the corpus included all of Wagner's operas as well as a large set of jazz improvisations, this search picks up not only the minor 7 flat 5 chords in the jazz examples, but the minor 7 flat 5 chords found in the opening bars in *Tristan and Isolde* (the so called "Tristan chord"). This would afford students a powerful insight into the ways in which similar sonorities are handled in different musical settings and styles.

As a final learning example, consider a scenario where a student wishes to find all examples of a minor 7th flat 5 chord that is followed by a dominant chord, in a II-V progression (i.e. in the key of C minor, a D minor 7th flat 5 chord followed by a G Dominant 7 chord). Using the same procedure as above to locate the chord structure, a dominant chord can be found. The challenge lies in finding where these two chords form a II-V progression. This can be accomplished by examining the distance between the frequencies located at the beginning of the set of distances characterizing the minor 7 flat 5 chord, and the frequency located at the beginning of the set of distances characterizing the dominant chord.

Searching data in this way allows some exciting possibilities in music pedagogy to start to emerge. It becomes far simpler to expose music students to correlations between different genres; it becomes far quicker to iterate through many differing examples. It allows students with different musical backgrounds (i.e. those with limited exposure to navigating complex orchestral scores) to explore different types of music.

Like any typical implementation of a search engine, it is also possible to keep a search history so students can track the things that have interested them most. If the database is linked to audio examples it also becomes possible to provide customized listening to students based on their searches (i.e. consider a scenario in where the examples returned from a student's search of all minor 7 flat 5 chords can be ported to an iPod or similar device). Finally, this type of searching allows user profiling to take place, (a growing phenomena preference systems [11,12]), so it becomes conceivable to data mine the searches that students undertake in order to create a shareable profile of those pieces of music in the corpus they prefer.

4. GOING FURTHER THAN SEARCHING: RECOMMENDATION

While it is useful to be able to implement a search engine for music data, is it possible to go further? Often it is productive to not only provide music students with a range of similar examples, but also with a mechanism by which to be able to directly compare their own work to

composers and improvisers whose works they are studying. Consider the problem of teaching students how to carry out counterpoint or multi-part harmony. Theorist and educator Kent Kennan notes that it is critical in such a situation, to ensure students understand that, a 'good melodic line [consists of] a sense of direction and a climax point, both of which contribute to a clear cut and interesting melodic contour...[as well as a] pleasing balance between conjunct and disjunct motion and ascending and descending motion' [13]. This is typical statement of many instructive music texts. Yet what does it actually mean? Qualities such 'as sense of direction' and 'climax point' are subjective. It is possible then, to take a different route? What if students were placed in a position, whether they are composing or improvising, of being able to view a possible set of choices of the next note in a phrase whilst they are in the process of creating a phrase, given what is happening in the corpus as a whole?

Using this data set to build some kind of recommender system is in some ways a complicated enterprise. The data set is good in the sense that it has no issues one would usually expect in a large data set such as data sparsity or any kind of data inflation. However at the same time, this data set is problematic. The first reason for this is that, if the data set is normalized and plotted in multi-dimensional space, note and rest events that are quite different in terms of their behavior through the corpus would sometimes cluster together. Consider the notes at (a.) and (b.) in Figure 5. They are very similar in some respects (i.e. frequency and duration), however in musical passages on-beats (seen here at a.) and off-beats (seen here at b.) tend to behave quite differently.

Figure 5

The second issue arises when considering those data points that should be regarded as similar, yet do not appear clustered closely when plotted in multi-dimensional space. Consider an example that was same in all respects as that listed in Figure 5, but transposed to key of F sharp major. Even though these would be very similar passages they would appear as markedly different. Related to this, consider how different absolute pitches operate depending on the setting in which they occur. The note middle C could be found in a passage that is in the key of G Major, C minor, or E flat major and would behave in markedly

different ways. Consequently, being able to use this data in a predictive manner requires that these issues somehow be accommodated.

Rather than calculating distances between note and rest events in multi-dimensional space, one alternative approach to his problem could be to collect certain attributes found in the data set, locate them in a tuple, and then find identical tuples across the corpus with a view to creating a list of the next possible note and rest events these tuples could lead to. It would then be possible to use weighted probability to calculate the likelihood that any note or rest event defined with an identical tuple could lead to certain other notes.

Figure 6

An example of a data structure to accommodate this is listed in Figure 6 and utilizes the same information found in the data set already converted from MusicXML. The attributes 'position_in_beat', 'position_in_bar' and 'duration', are drawn directly from the data set. The 'time_duration_of_beat' attribute is an actual time value, calculated using duration and tempo (being duration multiplied by tempo divided by 60).

Although previously the data set has utilized the attribute 'midi_frequency' to denote frequency, to implement recommendations, frequency will instead be denoted only in terms of a list of the minimized distances to other frequencies occurring at the same time in different parts of the same piece of music.

For example, if the note or rest event under consideration is the quarter note E (seen at (a.) in the Figure 7), its frequency is calculated by measuring the distance (modulo 12) between this note and any other notes occurring at the same in different parts time (seen at (b.) and (c.)) Note also that this distance is minimized: the distance to the other notes (here being a C and a G) is the distance to the closest C and closest G).

Figure 7

The data set is then converted into a set of tuples, an example of which can be seen in Figure 8. When looking over the entire corpus, it now becomes possible to find identical points at which this tuple occurs and to then investigate what happens next. If, for example, one hundred examples of the tuple were found across the corpus leading to three possibilities as to which note or rest events that could occur next, this could be returned to the user as a weighted probability to be used as recommendation.

Figure 8

This is perhaps one of the simplest ways to differentiate between different note and rest events in a corpus in order to introduce a notion of recommendation. However it does make it possible to discern similar data points across the corpus and to see where these data points lead.

There are of course issues here. It is not an ideal solution to simply return to a recommendation based on the highest probability, as this will certainly limit variety. Additionally, if every note or rest event in the corpus can be rendered as a tuple upon which recommendations can be made, when there are tuples occurring at the same time (derived from note or rest events in different parts that occur at the same time), which tuple's recommendation should be given precedence? The challenge with this approach is how to adjust the probability weightings. Possible solutions could include utilizing different parts of the corpus to influence probability weightings, or identifying common sequences of tuples, which could suggest recurring themes in the music and adjusting the weights based on this.

The possibility of suggesting recommendation based on the data set offers some exciting opportunities. Increasingly, music software packages (such as Logic Pro,

Cubase etc.) provide composers with a range of automated music creation tools (such as pre-recorded loops) to facilitate composition. The approach outlined above introduces the possibility of taking this a step further: to allow composers to be presented with different options around how their compositions might unfold as they write them, and even to have these recommendations be derived from the behavior of their own customized corpus. Additionally, utilizing a data set drawn from MusicXML has ramifications for the way in which music preference systems can be designed. Consider music streaming services such as Pandora, which rely on the manual categorization of different types of music in order that it can be data-mined: is it feasible to use MusicXML data mining to speed up this process?

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated a way in which MusicXML data can be used in order to create a mineable data set. It has shown how search functionality can be implemented across the data set and how it can be used for recommendation. This way of interacting with music provides a means by which students can gain very deep insights into a large corpus of music and develop strong musical intuitions based on concrete examples.

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